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**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
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**THE COLLAPSE OF LANGUAGE: AESTHETICIZING MORAL
DISINTEGRATION IN BERNARD-HENRI LÉVY'S LE DIABLE EN TÊTE**

Abstract. The philosophical aftermath of May 1968 witnessed a profound reckoning with the ideals and illusions of revolutionary thought, ushering in a shift in the rhetorical and stylistic modes through which French intellectuals expressed dissent and disillusionment in literature and life. Bernard-Henri Lévy's *Le Diable en Tête* is an example of literary texts in this category. This paper, therefore, critiques the novel with a multidisciplinary theoretical framework which combines post-structuralism literary theory, Nietzschean philosophy, and Jacques Derrida theory of *différance* to interrogate its representation of the collapse of language and moral disintegration. The paper explores the stylistic strategies through which the text linguistically constructs and aestheticizes the protagonist's moral and psychological collapse while debating how the text transforms destruction and disintegration into a compelling and beautiful narrative experience. Through textual analysis, the study finds out that Lévy deployed lyrical diction, syntactic fragmentation and philosophical abstraction, introspective narrative voice which is punctuated by aphoristic sentences, abrupt shifts in tone, and elaborate syntactic constructions, to reflect the protagonist's inner turmoil and moral ambivalence. Lévy's linguistic aestheticization raises critical questions about the relationship between style and morality, challenging readers to consider how beauty can mask, amplify, or complicate representations of evil and downfall. The paper concludes that rather than depicting collapse with straightforward despair or horror, Lévy positions the failure of language as a linguistic rebellion against ideological closure and as a performative expression of modern existential malaise making the readers confront with the paradox of beauty in ruin and engage with ethical decay as a complex, seductive process.

Key words: Collapse of language, fragmentation, existential nihilism, stylistic strategies, *le Diable en Tête*, Bernard-Henri Lévy (BHL)

INTRODUCTION

Spivak views literature as a site where ideology operates silently, shaping readers' perceptions through what is included, excluded, or marginalized. With the collapse of language, this study presents the ambivalence of language as an instrument of thought formation and expression thereby stimulating [re] actions in life and literature. To this end, language and literature have long been perceived as foundational pillars of human civilization thereby signaling different landmarks in the trajectory of human existence. This is because they have been serving as vehicles for transmitting culture, shaping identity, and fostering empathy. They are often credited with illuminating truths about the human condition and catalyzing social progress. While traditionally celebrated as tools of enlightenment, empathy, and moral reflection, language and literature can also perpetuate ideologies of oppression, manipulate truth, and contribute to social fragmentation. Similarly, they can negatively function as potent tools in the disservice to humanity as they become complicit in distorting reality and undermining human dignity. Considering the significant input of literature to human civilization, different themes have been satirizing or moralizing human societies with the dexterous use of language for communicative and aesthetic functions. The thematization of literary texts vary based on the peculiar sociological, political and historical experiences of respective authors as found in varied French and English literatures.

The collapse of moral, psychological and ideological certainties, for instance, is a recurring theme in 20th century French literature with the exemplification of Bernard-Henri Lévy's *Le Diable en tête* which elegantly aestheticises disintegration and the collapse of moral. Set against the backdrop of postwar trauma and intellectual rebellion, the novel traces the descent of Benjamin, a brilliant but disillusioned youth whose inner disarray mirrors the ideological fragmentation of his generation. While the novel's subject matter gravitates toward existential crisis, political violence, and emotional decay, the narrative is distinguished by its philosophical depth and the stylistic beauty with which collapse is rendered. The language of the novel- poetic, abstract and at times, almost liturgical- elevates ruin into an object of aesthetic fascination.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Le Diable en Tête by Bernard-Henri Lévy is a semi-autobiographical novel that tells the story of a young intellectual and wealthy Frenchman, Benjamin, born during the Nazi occupation, whose father was executed for collaborating with the regime. The narrative explores Benjamin's tumultuous journey from childhood to adulthood, through wartime in Paris and post-war in New York, becoming a left-wing terrorist and facing personal and political crises that ends in a suicide in Jerusalem. The novel opens with Benjamin's introspective awakening, both physical and existential. He confronts his body and mind as sites of tension because his

sensory experiences mixed with a growing detachment from the world. Benjamin reflects on his familial relationships, especially with his parents, whose histories and trauma haunt him. The impact of World War II looms large, shaping Benjamin's worldview and sense of inherited guilt or trauma. Benjamin immerses himself in the intellectual and political ferment of the 1960s and 1970s France. His involvement with radical ideas and youthful revolt is captured through fragmented narrative and philosophical reflection, depicting the clash between ideology and personal doubt. Benjamin confronts the failures of political idealism and the erosion of clear moral frameworks. His identity fractures under the weight of disillusionment represented through symbolic language and poetic imagery. The protagonist, adrift in the aftermath of cultural rebellion, embodies a loss of ethical orientation. The novel culminates in a meditation on silence, loss, and the dissolution of self. Benjamin's journey closes not with resolution but with an open-ended confrontation with emptiness and aestheticized ruin.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In Lévy's *Le Diable en Tête*, language functions not merely as a vehicle of narration but as a stylistic instrument of aestheticization. Through lyrical diction, elaborate syntax and philosophical abstraction, Lévy transforms the protagonist's moral and psychological collapse into a refined, and almost seductive experience. The tension between stylistic beauty and moral collapse problematizes conventional boundaries, narrative form and ethical content. This manifests in key stylistic features in the novel such as linguistic transformation, recursive syntax, elliptical and oblique language.

Linguistic fragmentation refers to a breakdown or disruption in the normal flow, structure, or coherence of language. Upholding Leech and Short's [2007] submission that deviating from normal patterns is to produce artistic or emotional effects, writers pushed language beyond conventional limits, playing with syntax, diction, and form to capture the fragmentation and complexity of modern consciousness and society. Lévy opts for classic, almost elevated language to reinforce the philosophical and historical weight of his story. In *Le Diable en Tête*, he does not employ language as a transparent medium of thought or ethical clarity rather he turns language into a mirror of a crumbling moral world, becoming an opaque surface, a tangle of evasions, mystifications, and aesthetic detachment. His lack of syntactic completeness heightens emotional impact as he uses fragmentation to mirror sarcastic or cynical detachment as stated in the expression: *c'était une blague, une farce* [p.296]. These fragmented sentences mirror the protagonist's fractured mental state as it reflects hesitation, uncertainty and existential doubt. On this, the following excerpt reveals thus:

Fallait-il noter la manière farouche qu'il a eue de m'envoyer paître quand je lui ai proposé d'aller voir *Clair de Terre* au cinéma ? Je ne sais pas. Je ne sais plus ce qu'il faut noter. [141]

The narrator often acknowledges the limits of his own expression, undermining the authority of language, he reminds himself that language is both his refuge and his prison even as he relies on it. The following excerpt reveals the situation as shown:

Et puis, brusquement, je le vois qui sans raison, se met à s'agiter, gesticuler, me faire pendant que je parle tout un tas de grimaces, de clowneries, de pieds-de-nez, de bouffonneries. Est-ce qu'il se moque de moi ? me dis-je. [p 249]

This self-reflexive moment highlights the performative collapse of language, making it indispensable and insufficient in the expression of the writer's experiences. The narrator's awareness of language's failure dramatizes his ethical and existential crisis, embodying the tension between expression and silence as found in the expression: *et tout est devenu clair* [p.27]. This sensual detail clashes with the introspective statement merging fleshy realism with existential revelation. And while reclaiming individual origin and moral spontaneity, Lévy rejects totalizing inheritance through the use of paratactic and parallel clauses. An instance of this situation is found in the following excerpt:

C'est pour bientôt, il le sent. Il m'a demandé pardon, ce matin, pour tout le mal qu'il m'a fait – pour tout celui qu'il fait, qu'il fera à notre fils. [p.112]

Recursive syntax opines the embedding of clauses within clauses or phrases within phrases. In the novel, recursive syntax reflects the narrator's obsessive introspection and the novel's philosophical density. Lévy's sentences often cascade like a philosophical stream of consciousness, layered with historical and metaphysical references. With the aim of echoing trauma, confusion and memory distortion, his short and punchy sentences unfold like philosophical aphorisms. At times, a sentence begins and then dissolves into silence or a breath interrupted or a thought vanishing before it ever takes form. The following excerpt reveals thus:

Lui parler? Le raisonner? Il n'entend pas. Il n'entend plus.
Je ne suis plus très sûre que nous parlions toujours la même langue. [p.37]

These sentences tend to spiral. They build layers of subjective interpretation-layering thought upon thought, ideas about ideas, feelings about feelings- signaling recursive psychological inquiry which blur logic and emotion. He uses these starkly juxtaposed statements to evoke psychological collapse as the syntax does not follow logical progression but mirrors shock.

Similarly, the novelist stylistically uses language to reveal linguistic opaqueness of inner thoughts and extrinsic expressions of the writer through mechanisms of language. His long, winding and recurring sentences with overloading punctuation (comma and semi-colons) create subordinate clauses with

dense rhythm, rhetorical flourishes, and philosophical jargon. This is shown in the following excerpt:

La prochaine fois, c'est décidé: je pleure, je hurle, je m'enfuis toute nue sur l'avenue, ou je me fais un rempart du corps de son fils – mais pas ça, plus ça, plus de ces odieuses'etreintes wui me donnent la nausée jusqu'au matin. [p. 38]

The excerpt above resists immediate comprehension and demand close rereading. The spiraling syntax reflects not only mental confusion but the collapse of meaning itself. Also, early in the novel, the narrator's inner turmoil is reflected in long, recursive sentences that accumulate subordinate clauses, mirroring a fracturing psyche. The effect is a form of estrangement and an aesthetic that reflects the protagonist's alienation from the world and from language itself. On this, the following excerpt reveals thus:

Mais la nouveauté, maintenant, c'est que ça ne s'arrêtait pas; que la vague, une fois lancée, semblait ne plus vouloir refluer, que c'était comme une marée folle, sauvage, sans règle ni retour; et que tout se passait comme si un manipulateur fou m'avait noué, vrillé les nerfs les uns aux autres en une sorte de court-circuit qui m'électrisait tout entière. [p.11]

The narrator's attempt to grasp a coherent truth is thwarted by the self-referential nature of his thoughts, embodying Derrida's notion of *différance* that meaning is perpetually deferred and destabilized.

Foregrounding on Heidegger submission of language being a medium of self-expression and inner thought, Levy positions language as an obstacle rather than a link with the use of ellipses to indicate gaps in the narrator's thought. He challenges conventional assumptions about linguistic transparency and suggests that in conditions of moral disintegration, language itself becomes complicit in mystification and ethical evasion as found in the expressions: *Bloque. Bouche. [p.12], Tritesse. Angoisse [p.126], La mère. Le premier mari. Le second. Le fils enfin. [p.200]*. These elliptical constructions lack main verbs and function as isolated noun phrases to emphasize loss and existential emptiness as they mirror the abruptness of traumatic memory and the narrator's inability to form coherent thoughts during moments of crisis. The following excerpt reveals the situation

Et cette autre chose, je suis désolée, ça ne peut être que ça :
Jean et moi... moi et Jean... notre arrivée... sa manière d'être avec moi..... la façon qu'il avait – et qui les épatait toutes – de m'offrir une coupe de champagne.... ce drôle de sourire

narquois, mais entendu, qu'il prenait pour me présenter.....
bref, les idées que toutes ces idiots ont forcément dû se
faire... [p.55]

The situation is further revealed as follows:

Le front donc...L'angle busqué du nez...La courbe de l'épaule...
Le ventre...La jambe...Le fuselage de la cuisse...Là, dans l'entre-
deux...just a glance... furtif, s'il vous plaît... c'est comme ça que
c'est efficace.... Il y a bien cette satanée bouche, toujours, qu'il
vaut mieux éviter...Mais tant pis pour la bouche...On se passera
de bouche... Il faut aller de l'avant... [p. 62-63]

In excerpts, the failure of language to serve as a transparent medium for communication is presented with resistance to the meaning of words. The ellipses represent memory lapses or emotional overwhelm to put the reader directly into the character's emotional space. The elliptical reference to body parts. The excerpts further serve to highlight the fragmented perception of reality and self, and the failure of coherent language. This listing of body features mimics the obsessive recollection of someone remembered. Seeing only fragments and not a whole sentence is possibly due to trauma or grief and suggest that the narrator is haunted.

Lévy's technique of language use also depicts a reflexive moment where language is overloaded, yet meaning remains concealed. His stylistic over-determination through the use of possible expressive and ostentatious form, ironically deepen ethical opacity and create semantic overload that cancels itself. A clear example of this argument is found in the following excerpt.

Lui a au moins un mérite: il se laisse aimer; il me
laisse rever; il sait qu'il n'y a pas de secret; il
n'essaie pas de comprendre pourquoi c'est ce geste-
ci, cette attitude là... [p. 65]

Here, language ceases to connect; rather than being a bridge, it becomes a barrier which gives room to meaning to slip away and thought loses itself in its own winding paths. As if BHL had wanted to condense all the resources of written expression, the sentences: "il se laisse aimer; il me laisse rever" point to a paradox that signals the failure of language to communicate meaning. Also, by emphasizing "il sait qu'il n'y a pas de secret;", Lévy suggests that human truth resists linguistic capturing. This suggests a moral skeptical stance that intimacy and virtue are beyond articulation.

Saussure views language as a system of signs, where meaning comes not from reference to the real world, but from differences between signs. At times, as a form of postmodern uncertainty, Levy reduced questions to nominal fragments or subordinate clauses without conjugated verb to problematize the idea of eloquence. With this, he transforms active inquiries into abstract objects. This stylistics device questions whether inquiry itself has meaning any longer, thus, challenging the notion

that questions naturally lead to understanding. This shift, however, reflects the collapse of traditional language function as language no longer structure reality as found in the following excerpts:

Quoi? Deja, si vite, la vie qui commence? [p.27]

Pourquoi ? Comment ? A cause de lui ou de moi ? [p. 61]

These excerpts which mirror the protagonist's psychic and moral collapse, reflect the collapse of traditional language functions. These are not questions meant to be answered but labelled for uncertainty and metaphysical voids. BHL shrinks questions to nominal fragments to display the narrator's incomplete thoughts as being suspended in isolation. This shift is an integral part of BHL's aesthetics of disintegration.

According to Childs [2008], modernism sets out to reject the conventions of 19th-century realism, linear narratives, and stable identities to embraces experimentation, ambiguity, and a search for new forms of expression. Thus, modernist writers' exploration of these limitations, ambiguities, and failures often results in semantic ambiguity as a narrative style. Semantic ambiguity occurs when a sentence or phrase can be interpreted in more than one way either because of polysemy, vague reference or deliberate syntactic openness. Judging by Jacques Derrida's concept of *différance* and the inherent instability of meaning in language, Lévy frequently employs terms loaded with philosophical subtexts which include, "le diable (358)" "*la vraie* [p 338]" "*la trahison* [453]," which are never established into fixed meanings to echo moral relativism. 'Le diable' in the title is both literal and metaphorical, symbolizing inner demons, ideological struggles, or the complexities of corrupting ideas that haunt the human mind which reveals the situation as represented in the novel.

The following excerpt reveals thus:

On passait au domaine de la passion, presque de la religion!
les fedayin eux-mêmes étaient des idoles de chair aux pieds
desquelles il se prosternait. Le peuple palestinien tout entier
une sorte de peuple-christ dont la misère, le malheur, portaient
témoignage pour l'ensemble de l'humanité. Et quant à Israël
ce n'était plus un Etat comme un autre, éventuellement justiciable
d'un sévère réquisitoire politique : c'était le Mal, le Diable en
personne. [p.372]

Aligning with Saussure's view, BHL creates meaning through contrasts, juxtapositions, and the play of opposites. "Le diable" in the excerpt functions as a stylistic figure (metaphor) for language's seductive power that simultaneously reveals and conceals truth. This affirms that words and meanings exist only through their difference from other words and not by pointing to real-world referents. And as Wittgenstein [1953] and Austin [1962] submit that language is meaningful when it performs actions which connect and build social bond, the opposite occur as Levy renders language impotent and depersonalized *in* *Le Diable en tête*. The protagonist speaks without consequence and grows more isolated the more he speaks creating

the possibility of communication collapse as seen in the expression: “Lui parler ? Le raisonner ? Il n’entend pas. Il n’entend plus.” [p.37]. Lévy’s metaphorical use of “le diable” corroborates Nietzsche’s [1999] perception of surpassing conventional morality to embrace complexity, and shapes personal identity and values. He consumes the claims that Christianity and democracy are products of slave morality by presenting the devil as a physical being that lives in the society. The following excerpt reveals thus:

J'ai beau savoir qu'il a fait Centrale lui aussi, connaître ses talents d'ingénieur, me dire que c'est « de ce cocktail de science et de national-socialisme que sortira (sic) la forme de l'Europe de demain » – pour moi ça ne change rien : si j'avais à me figurer le visage du diable en personne c'est de ses traits, il me semble, que je songerais à m'inspirer. [p.43]

The devil is not an external demon or an invisible being, but that inner murmur that seduces and tears apart, that voice which steals truth beneath a veil of deceptive beauty.

Ambiguous use of metaphors linked to life as an enigmatic forest, a face carrying an epoch, the mind as a battleground and the figure of the devil as a symbol both of temptation and intellectual seduction resists clear moral categorization. The recurring use of devil-related imagery in metaphors functions stylistically as a symbol of intellectual and moral struggle to intensify the atmosphere of internal conflict. Below is the excerpt which reveals the situation:

Et puis ma conviction, enfin, que je ne demande à personne de partager, mais qui me désarme: c'est toujours la mort qui gagne ... et le mal... et le diable... et ce diable-ci en particulier que je connais mieux que quiconque pour m'être mis sous son autorité. [p.473]

The narrator’s confession of broken certainties through his description of the slipping away of the surrounding world, draws out the illusion of clarity even while embracing confusion. This emphasizes alienation and the impossibility of grounding responsibility in external or internal anchors. The following excerpt also reveals the situation:

Serait-ce que le corps se lasse de trop longtemps désirer ? Que le désir lui-même s'use à rêver ainsi, en vain, d'objets qui se dérobent ? Ou est-ce le parti pris d'en finir au contraire – et la certitude que, ce soir, quoi qu'il arrive, je l'aurai séduit – qui fait que, déjà, je me sens l'aimer un peu moins ? [p.61]

With the stylistic use of language, Lévy also presents ideo-philosophical schisms in personality development owing to previous and nascent experiences which have predetermined the perception of reality. The emptiness of Benjamin’s

words parallels the collapse of meaningful communication as speech though hollow, functions as mere gesture and performative. The situation, as taken from the text, is found below:

Je suppose que de savoir – de croire au moins – que le monde me suivra, qu'il mourra derrière moi, m'aidera à franchir le pas. Je suppose aussi que de ne tenir à rien, à personne, de ne plus vraiment me situer dans l'ordre réglé du monde, de ne plus vraiment faire sens avec la prose des choses, rend le geste facile encore et comme naturel. Mais je crois surtout qu'il y a trop d'ardeur encore dans la peur... Trop de ferveur... Trop de fièvre... Trop d'émoi... Il faut être un vivant pour avoir peur de mourir. [p.503]

Here, Benjamin no longer recognizes the principles that once guided his actions. Fidelity, commitment, love—all seem to collapse into a void where indifference reigns. He speaks, but his words are empty of conviction, like gestures repeated without substance. The world around him slips away, and with it, all possibility of responsibility. This situation is found in the following excerpt:

Seulement voilà, il y a une chose que Benjamin avait oublié de prévoir : c'est qu'on approchait du 15 février; que le 15 février était la date de son anniversaire; que Marie allait, comme autrefois, vouloir le couvrir de cadeaux; qu'en bonne bourgeoise qu'elle était, bien à cheval sur les principes, elle répugnerait à les payer sur l'argent qu'il lui confiait; et qu'elle ne trouverait rien de mieux que de les régler elle-même par des chèques tirés sur son compte en banque strasbourgeois. [p.434]

The above excerpt encapsulates the novel's philosophical pessimism about ethics and subjectivity in a fragmented, post-ideological era. Benjamin's loss of recognition of "les principes" signals moral disintegration as values which were once foundational become void, leaving only indifference.

The manipulation of narrative structure and style enacts the collapse of meaning while positioning a work of art as both a critique and a symptom of moral disintegration. Critiquing Childs' modernist theory of a coherent message or voice, McHale's opines that readers should encounter shifting, unreliable narrators and textual ambiguity. To this end, many 20th-century novels such as Joyce's *Ulysses* (famous for its fragmented narrative structure, shifting time frames, and episodic style) and William Faulkner's *The Sound and the Fury* (famous for its multiple narrators and non-linear timelines to depict a family's decline) reject linear, and chronological storytelling but use fragmented narratives, multiple perspectives, and disjointed time frames to express their thoughts. *Le Diable en Tête* mixes philosophical essay, memoir, and narrative storytelling to make the narrative style hybrid and fluid. This collapse of narrative coherence mimics the failure of moral direction by undermining traditional narrative coherence, which aligns with postmodern and psychoanalytic literary modes as shown in the following

expressions: se mettre... dans la peau [p.357], d'un vieillard cacochyme [p.404], d'une jeune catholique [p.115], ou encore [p.135] de Benjamin (p.190), éternel mari [p.114]. Lévy's ability to use voices that range from bitter to sensual and philosophical to political add a polyphonic layering and texture to his style. The narrative voice oscillates between ironic detachment and intense introspection, creating a stylistic tension that underpins the novel's exploration of madness and temptation. The following excerpts reveal the situation. The following excerpt reveals thus:

Si j'ai éprouvé le besoin d'ouvrir ce nouveau cahier, ce n'est pas pour le seul plaisir de faire le point de mes opinions, de mes états d'âme ou de ce qui demeure de ma jeunesse. Mais c'est, comme d'habitude, comme chaque fois que cela m'est arrivé dans le passé, pour une raison précise. Pressante.
[p.117]

The situation is further revealed as follows:

dont je t'accorde, encore une fois, qu'elles ne nous sont pas immédiatement familières; dont je saisis encore assez mal, moi-même, le lien secret qui les unit ; mais qui sont comme l'édifice invisible qui justifie et soutient un si prodigieux dessein... Beth s'y est attelée, je crois; et je te communiquerai son rapport sitôt que je l'aurai. [p.258]

The above excerpts exemplify the novel's disjointed narrative, where the past is inaccessible and history disintegrates, mirroring linguistic and moral collapse.

Lévy's *Le Diable en Tête* employs a deliberate fragmentation of narrative voice that reflects the protagonist's fractured identity and the novel's broader thematic concern with moral and linguistic disintegration. He constructs the novel as a polyphonic mosaic—diary entries, interviews, letters, and finally the protagonist's confession. The narrator's voice which is intimate and reflective sometimes becomes confrontational, pulling readers into his thought process. Judging by Hutcheon's conclusion that postmodernism questions the idea of the unified subject and the omnipotent author, replacing them with fragmented identities and multiple perspectives, at times, the narration moves into imagined or real dialogues with other thinkers, creating a conversational yet argumentative style. This multiplicity disrupts narrative unity, destabilizes the notion of a singular, authoritative voice in order to reinforce the uniqueness and subjectivity of the narrator's experience. The narrative presented in the form of a journal, a letter and a blurred memory intertwines without clear connection, voices collide, are interrupted, and truth fades in a labyrinth of discourse. An example illustrating this argument is presented below:

Plus la peine de chercher. Il a trouvé. Tout trouvé. Et je crois que c'est le dernier mot, de ma vie, que j'écrirai dans un journal. [p. 144]

The protagonist is not a consistent identity but a composite of multiple, incompatible selves – Benjamin, his mother, his lover, a Parisian friend, and his step-father terrorist. He no longer knows where his story begins, nor even if it is worth telling. Voices collide, are interrupted, and truth disappears in a web of discourse. This situation is revealed in the following excerpt:

Excerpt:

- Toute cette histoire, commencé-je, ne tient pas...
- Comment cela, « ne tient pas » ?
- Non, on n'y croit pas... On n'arrive pas à y croire... Comme s'il manquait quelque chose... Une nuance... Un détail... Une pièce dans votre puzzle qui...
- Au fait, je vous prie !
- Je ne sais pas très bien, justement... Vos rapports déjà... Cette haine dont il vous poursuit et qui le conduira...
- Je vous ai tout dit là-dessus. Vous avez eu votre content de petites histoires.
- Des petites histoires, c'est vrai. Beaucoup de petites histoires. Mais pas vraiment de raisons finalement, d'explications de fond...
- Je pensais que c'était votre partie, ça, « le fond ». Moi je vous ai livré le brut.
- C'est cela. Mais à propos de « faits » précisément : ce départ, cette brouille si soudaine... [p. 225 – 226]

Here, the narrator's uncertainty about the boundaries of the story and the presence of voices that are not his own destabilizes the coherence of a singular narrative perspective. This multi-perspectivity undermines narrative authority and highlights the collapse of a unified self.

This fragment highlights the protagonist's alienation from himself, a key element in the novel's depiction of moral and linguistic collapse. In the novel, Lévy deploys a literary style that is deliberately disjointed, abstract, and often hermetic. He deliberately disrupts coherent narrative by denying his protagonist any continuity or resolution. The shifting voices underscore the fragmentation of Benjamin's identity and his oscillation between roles and eras. The protagonist's identity becomes a performance. He plays roles as a lover, student and dissenter without inhabiting the roles authentically. Each of these roles offer a partial, conflicting glimpse of Benjamin, underscoring the elusiveness of both character and truth. The opening line “Au bout de ce visage, il y avait le siècle. [p.8]” describes Benjamin's face as personifying the figurative phrase “le siècle” as a passion of personal identity with entire historical epochs. This line give dignity and importance to Benjamin.

The stylistic fragmentation of disintegration of identity is not merely a formal experiment but it reflects the novel's central philosophical concern of the breakdown of coherent moral and ideological frameworks in post-1968 France. The narrator questions and eventually unravel the traditional values, political certainties, and

collective belief systems that had long shaped French society. The following excerpt reveals the situation.

Et c'est le moment, je crois bien, où j'ai pour la première fois réalisé la profondeur du fossé qui nous sépareit – Est-ce que ça ne va pas rentrer dans l'ordre à Paris, avec la rentrée ? – Non, justement! Car il rapporte cette lèpre à Paris, je vous l'ai dit, où elle va orienter, désormais, l'essentiel de ses comportements. Je ne vais pas vous raconter les choses en détail. Mais ce que je peux vous dire c'est qu'il lui faut de l'argent, par exemple, pour se payer les concerts, les posters, les disques surtout qui sont devenus, pour lui, une véritable drogue. [p.189]

The situation is further revealed as follows:

Le plus bouleversant c'est peut-être cette violence que je découvre en moi et dont je n'avais, je le jure, jamais rien soupçonné. Car d'où viennent-ils donc, mon Dieu, ces cris ? Ces gestes de fureur ? Ce goût de frapper, de mordre, de déchirer ? Est-ce en moi qu'il est cet appétit de vengeance? Oui, je crois bien que c'est de la vengeance qui me pousse parfois à... Toutes les femmes savent ça, j'imagine. Moi, je le découvre. [p.65]

Here, Benjamin articulates his youthful search for meaning amid ideological chaos. The contrast between revolt and silence reflects the tension between action and existential questioning. The protagonist is trapped in a state of self-misrecognition. He sees himself as intelligent, aloof, and aesthetically refined, but this self-image masks deeper incoherence. He is a subject of a realm of illusions, identifications, and narcissism.

Lévy's stylistic use of language and metaphors evokes inherited trauma and fragmented identity that links Benjamin's self to collective history and the ruins left by war. Echoing Lacanian notions of the fragmented "I" and the elusive "real" self, the protagonist does not simply speak disjointedly; he exists disjointedly. The following excerpt further elucidates this view.

Je veux dire par là que je ne peux plus entrer dans un lit avec lui sans qu'il commence par me tâter maintenant. Me palper. Me tourner, me retourner. Me humer. Me flairer. M'examiner sous toutes les coutures. Me soupeser du geste et du regard. Me goûter comme si j'étais un vin. Me tripoter comme si j'étais une bête. Me faire ronfler, presque vrombir comme un moteur. [p.292]

Each reflection returns a distorted, multiple, elusive image to symbolize a self that cannot be resolved or fully known, intensifying the novel's exploration of existential disintegration. Benjamin searches for a stable face, an essence, but finds

only masks that shatter at the slightest touch. He becomes an unfinished puzzle as each piece is rejected by the very hand that tries to grasp it. The following excerpt buttresses this view:

C'est la même trouble jouissance d'être cette créature fugace tout à coup, fantomatique, insaisissable – pas vue, pas prise – et assurée, pour ainsi dire, d'une espèce d'impunité. Mais la différence, pourtant, c'est qu'à l'époque des canulars nous nous amusons comme des folles. Alors que là, malgré tout, et une fois passés ces rares et brefs moments de plaisir, je souffre comme une damnée. [p.296]

The protagonist's struggle to piece together his past reflects a broader theme of historical and personal fragmentation. The metaphor highlights Benjamin's fractured identity and the images reveal that the 'self' resists unification. Conversely, language being performative and dispersed rather than coherent, becomes a mechanism of remedying psychological and sociological fragmentations. The language fragments and obscures meaning rather than clarifies it, effectively aestheticizing confusion and moral ambiguity. The image conveys the fragility and impermanence of memory. The metaphor frames memory not as a site of recovery or identity formation, but as one of absence and erosion as found in the expression: *Le visage rouge, violet, tuméfié sous les talons qui l'écrasent... Les membres brisés, réduits en charpie* [p 29]. The excerpt emphasizes fragmentation and alienation in personal relations as it expresses Benjamin's emotional isolation despite human contact. However, the aesthetic richness of Lévy's *Le Diable en Tête* is not a celebration of beauty but a performance of breakdown because eloquence masks ethical emptiness, and style becomes a vehicle for disorientation as found in *Je suis un monster* [p.69]

With Benjamin's fluid and unstable identity, the metaphor 'une foule en folie' [p.29] evokes multiplicity, fragmentation and collapse, nevertheless the rhythm is impressively balanced. Lévy encapsulates ideological and self-collapse in a single, elegant sentence. The sentence, which is not just a narrative content but a beautifully articulated linguistic collapse, draws the reader into a poetic appreciation of what is, essentially, a complete disintegration of self.

Foregrounding on the theories of aestheticism and the works of Nietzsche, Lyotard and Sontag, Lévy in *Le Diable en Tête* explores the tension between beauty and moral content. His sumptuous and complex prose style, laden with philosophical allusions and intricate syntax, serves as a stylistic counterpoint to the novel's themes of disintegration. The use of multiple testimonies reflects decay in narrative truth as there is no singular, coherent story, only divergent, sometimes incompatible accounts. This mimics the rotting core of grand narratives, where solidity disintegrates into fragments. The novel which opens with Mathilde's diary, recounting Benjamin's birth during wartime and her trauma with Édouard's betrayal and execution, ends with Benjamin speaking for himself in a written confession, which reframes everything as part of his quest for redemption of another dimension of his selfhood. BHL deviates structural and pragmatic rules in support of Foucault's

criticism of a continuous history of ideas and replaces it with a discontinuous, fragmented view of knowledge. One of the most striking features of Lévy's *Le Diable en Tête* is the way it blurs existential pain with poetic beauty, revealing that the collapse of language is not accidental, but aestheticized. Sentences are carefully constructed to reflect a post-ideological landscape in which truth, justice, and even meaning itself are suspended. The style aestheticizes meaninglessness as moral decay is not just described, but felt in the language's inability to stabilize meaning. This aesthetic excess becomes a form of ethical displacement as beauty and style mask the void left by the collapse of moral certainty. Many sentences show how Lévy crafts an aesthetic of decay through metaphor, rhythm, and philosophical tone. The narrative voice glides between beauty and ruin rendering collapse as an experience worthy of admiration. The following excerpt further illustrates this argument.

À la fin de la journée, pourtant, tout est devenu clair quand j'ai senti entre mes cuisses cet écoulement tiède, un peu poisseux, don't j'avais depuis un an perdu le souvenir...Quoi? Deja, si vite, la vie qui commence? [p.27]

The above excerpt captures Benjamin's bodily awakening and existential ambivalence. Levy's rich, corporeal transforms bodily renewal into a moment tinged with melancholic collapse, rendering personal disintegration emotionally and aesthetically potent. The language of return "la vie qui recommence" is rendered not with joy but with unsettling warmth (tiède), stickiness (poisseux) and utmost psychological repulsion. Yet, Levy's tone remains lyrical, suggestive of rebirth or awakening. In the novel, language becomes more concerned with style than truth. This upholds Derridean instability that words do not point to fixed referents for meaning can never be fixed but can be deferred or fractured. In this burst of rhetoric, where each word tries to shine brighter than the last, hides the void of a ruined morality, a hollow beauty that slips away beyond appearances. This situation is given in the following excerpt.

On était vendredi soir, je te le rappelle. Le cadavre de Pierrot n'était pas encore refroidi. Et tout ce joli monde partait, comme si de rien n'était, pour un week-end de ski organisé par le comité d'entreprise au col de la Faucille. [p.318]

Here, language performs the very disintegration it ostensibly conceals. Levy's diction softens horror with lyricism interpreting failure as a practice worthy of unsettlingly. The father's death haunts the family psyche; the decaying corpse works through memory and silence to symbolize trauma that refuses closure.

The modernist novel redefines time, space, and character interiority [Bradbury 120]. And as Rabaté argues, modernist texts foreground the failure of language to fully signify cracks in rational structures [p 67]. Through elevated diction and metaphor, moral ruin and philosophical catastrophe are not described in regular

moralism but in lyrical tones that amplify attraction rather than judgment of acts as shown in the following excerpt.

A la fin de la journée, pourtant, tout est devenu clair quand j'ai senti entre mes cuisses cet écoulement tiède, un peu poisseux, dont j'avais depuis un an perdu le souvenir... Quoi ? Déjà, si vite, la vie qui recommence? La chair qui, insolente, retrouve ses saisons? Tout ce chambardement rentré sagement dans l'ordre?[p.27]

This decaying beauty shows decomposition. Lévy finds a form of art that celebrates ruin without judging it and this transforms loss into an aesthetic experience. The beauty described is fascinating and melancholic and it reveals the novel's ambivalent stance toward decline. This signals an aesthetic that refuses moral evaluation, embracing disintegration as an object of contemplation rather than condemnation.

Lévy's syntax performs psychological rupture as it solidifies language collapse as a skill commendable for meditation. His use of syntax becomes even more disjointed in a quasi-stream-of-consciousness reflection as he collapses language in stages for a narrative style. Paradoxically, this cumulative structured sentence is elegant and symmetrical. The language collapse is orderly and carefully staged and sculpted as a stylized emptiness. While dismantling the conventions of plot, character, and clarity, Lévy presents a situation where words carry beauty even as they dissolve meaning. He dramatizes the loss of meaning in a world haunted by failed ideologies and moral paralysis. As Norris explains, deconstruction does not destroy meaning but reveals the tensions and faultiness in texts that pretend to be in unity. Instead of harmony or renewal, the novel finds artistry in fragmentation, loss, and moral ambiguity which is a key to understanding Lévy's literary project.

CONCLUSION

This paper has examined Bernard-Henri Lévy's *Le Diable en Tête* as a literary embodiment of moral collapse, aestheticized through a distinctive and philosophically charged prose style. Drawing on psychoanalytic theory, the paper reveals how the protagonist's moral inertia and aesthetic detachment are rooted in deeper structures of repression, dissociation, and linguistic disintegration. The central argument of this paper has been that Lévy in the novel does not simply portray ethical disintegration but enacts it. Lévy dismantles communicative norms, subverts referentiality, and aestheticizes linguistic opacity. The paper argues that recognizing the potential of language and literature to harm is a crucial step toward reclaiming their transformative power in the service of humanity. His deliberate collapse of language, a refusal of narrative resolution, and a stylization of emotional and moral decay, enables the construction of a literary universe in which the crisis of meaning is not remedied, but amplified and aestheticized. Drawing from the decadent tradition, the novel transforms moral and psychological collapse into a seductive literary surface where beauty becomes complicit. Lévy's narrative style masks crisis, and elegance conceals emptiness as the reader is lured into an experience of decay so finely wrought that it becomes pleasurable, even as it resists

ethical reconciliation. As the novel ends with no affirmative answers but offers the spectacle of their breakdown, this paper concludes with these rhetorical questions: Can language retain moral force in a culture of irony, detachment, and postmodern ambiguity? Is aesthetic beauty capable of resisting the seductions of moral indifference, or does it inevitably mask ethical failure? Can the Self remain coherent in a world where meaning has been evacuated from both speech and action? Ultimately, when harnessed for manipulation, exclusion, or the reinforcement of oppressive ideologies, linguistic and literary practices may contribute to confusion, alienation, and ethical decay among humanity.

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КРАХ ЯЗЫКА: ЭСТЕТИЗАЦИЯ МОРАЛЬНОГО РАЗЛОЖЕНИЯ В РОМАНЕ БЕРНАРА-АНРИ ЛЕВИ LE DIABLE EN TÊTE

Аннотация. Философские последствия событий мая 1968 года ознаменовались глубоким переосмыслением идеалов и иллюзий революционного мышления, что привело к сдвигу в риторических и стилистических способах выражения французскими интеллектуалами несогласия и разочарования в литературе и жизни. Роман Бернара-Анри Леви *Le Diable en Tête* является примером литературного произведения, относящегося к этому направлению. Настоящая статья анализирует роман с помощью междисциплинарной теоретической модели, сочетающей постструктуралистскую литературную теорию, философию Ницше и теорию *différance* Жака Деррида, чтобы исследовать, как в произведении представлено крушение языка и моральное разложение.

Статья рассматривает стилистические стратегии, посредством которых текст лингвистически конструирует и эстетизирует моральное и психологическое падение главного героя, а также анализирует, как разрушение и распад трансформируются в увлекательный и эстетически выразительный нарративный опыт. В результате текстуального анализа выявляется, что Леви использует лирическую лексику, синтаксическую фрагментацию и философскую абстракцию, интроспективную повествовательную манеру, прерываемую афористическими высказываниями, резкими сменами интонации и усложненными синтаксическими конструкциями — всё это отражает внутренние метания и моральную амбивалентность героя.

Эстетизация языка у Леви поднимает важные вопросы о связи между стилем и моралью, побуждая читателя задуматься над тем, как красота может скрывать, усиливать или усложнять образы зла и падения. В заключение автор приходит к выводу, что Леви не изображает крушение в виде прямолинейного отчаяния или ужаса, а рассматривает языковую несостоятельность как

лингвистический бунт против идеологического замыкания и как перформативное выражение современной экзистенциальной тревоги, заставляя читателя столкнуться с парадоксом красоты в разрушении и воспринимать моральный распад как сложный, но соблазнительный процесс.

Ключевые слова: крах языка, фрагментация, экзистенциальный нигилизм, стилистические стратегии, *Le Diable en Tête*, Бернар-Анри Леви (BHL)

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TILNING INQIROZI: BERNARD-ANRI LÉVYNING LE DIABLE EN TÊTE ASARI ASOSIDA AXLOQIY INQIROSNİ ESTETİKALASHTIRISH

Annotatsiya. 1968-yil may oyidagi inqilobiy voqealardan so'ng fransuz intellektual hayotida inqilobiy g'oyalar va ularning illuziyalari bilan chuqur falsafiy hisob-kitob boshlandi. Bu esa norozilik va umidsizlikni adabiyot va hayotda ifodalashning ritorik hamda uslubiy shakllarida sezilarli o'zgarishlarga olib keldi. Bernard-Anri Léving *Le Diable en Tête* ("Jin boshda") asari ushbu turkumga kiruvchi adabiy matnlardan biridir. Shu sababli, ushbu maqolada roman poststrukturalistik adabiyot nazariyasi, Nitsche falsafasi hamda Jak Derridaning *différance* nazariyasini birlashtirgan ko'p fanli nazariy asos orqali tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada asarda tilning qulashini va axloqiy inqirozni qanday ifodalagani o'rganiladi. Maqolada qahramonning axloqiy va psixologik tanazzulini til vositasida qanday estetik shaklda qurish va ifodalash uslublarini tahlil qiladi. Shuningdek, matn qanday qilib vayronagarchilik va yemirilishni estetik jozibadorlik bilan hikoya shakliga aylantirayotganini baholaydi. Matn tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, Lévy lirik lug'at boyligi, sintaktik parchalanganlik, falsafiy mavhumlik, aforistik gaplar bilan boyitilgan ichki monologga asoslangan hikoya uslubi, keskin ohang o'zgarishlari va murakkab gap tuzilmalari orqali bosh qahramonning ichki iztiroblari va axloqiy ikkiyoqlamaliligini ifodalaydi. Léving til orqali estetik ifodasi uslubi bilan axloq o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni muhokama qilishga undaydi — go'zallik qanday qilib yovuzlik va halokat tasvirlarini yashirishi, kuchaytirishi yoki murakkablashtirishi mumkinligini o'ylashga chorlaydi. Maqolada Lévy halokatni oddiy tushkunlik yoki dahshat bilan emas, balki tilning yemirilishini mafkuraviy yopilishga qarshi til isyoni sifatida va zamonaviy ekzistensial bezovtalikning performativ ifodasi sifatida talqin qilishi ochib berilgan. Bu esa o'quvchini vayrona ichidagi go'zallik paradoksi bilan yuzlashtirib, axloqiy yemirilishning murakkab va jozibali jarayon sifatida anglanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: tilning qulash jarayoni, fragmentatsiya, ekzistensial nihilizm, uslubiy strategiyalar, *Le Diable en Tête*, Bernard-Anri Lévy (BHL).